

Web-Based Career Guidance and Development Portal

K.M.W. Pathirana¹

*Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce
University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka*

¹kaveeshasn@gmail.com, ²kgdigamage@gmail.com, ³asankalilaan@gmail.com ,
⁴shantha@sjp.ac.lk

Abstract

The Web-Based Career Guidance and Development Portal was developed to enhance the efficiency and accessibility of career advisory services at the University of Sri Jayewardenepura. The existing manual system at the Career Guidance Unit (CGU) presented several challenges, including inefficiencies in appointment scheduling, delays in resume reviews, difficulties in tracking student career progress, and communicating career-related opportunities to students. To address these issues, we designed and developed a centralized, automated platform that integrates key features such as appointment scheduling, AI-assisted career guidance, resume generation and reviews, real-time notifications, and career progress tracking. By replacing manual workflows with a web-based solution, the portal facilitates improved collaboration between students and career advisors to ensure a more efficient and accessible career guidance process. The development process followed the Waterfall model of the System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) which incorporated phases starting from system analysis, moving on to system design, development, followed by testing and evaluation to ensure the final solution met user requirements effectively. The system was developed using technologies, including React for frontend development, Node.js with Express for backend, and MySQL for database management. AI-driven features were also integrated to provide students with automated interview practice and personalized career support. The implementation of this system significantly improved the services of the CGU, streamlining the process for both students and advisors. The system's ability to automate key functions reduced administrative overhead while enhancing the quality of career guidance services. Feedback from testing has shown that the platform meets the intended objectives effectively, and it has the potential to positively impact the career readiness of students.

Keywords: *Career Guidance, Appointment Scheduling, Resume Generation, Career Progress Tracking, AI-Assistance, Waterfall Model*